

PATH ANALYSIS STUDIES IN DESI COTTON (*Gossypium arboreum* L.)

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Abstract

This experiment was carried out with 30 hybrids of cotton in randomized complete block design (RCBD) with two replications at Cotton Research Station, MB Farm, Parbhani, 2023-24. Each plot consisted of one row of 6 m length and observations were recorded on five randomly selected plants from each genotype per replication for characters viz., plant height (cm), number of monopodia plant per plant, number of sympodia plant per plant, number of bolls plant per plant, boll weight (g), seed index (g), lint index (g) and seed cotton yield plant per plant (g). The characters viz., Days to 50% flowering, ginning out turn (%), Upper half mean length (mm), micronaire ($\mu\text{g}/\text{inch}$), and uniformity ratio were recorded on plot basis. Correlation and path coefficient analysis were worked out for 12 characters among 30 hybrids of arboreum cotton. Correlation studies revealed that boll weight, sympodia per plant, bolls per plant, plant height, uniformity ratio, fibre strength, ginning out turn and upper half mean length recorded significant positive association with seed cotton yield per plant. Further partitioning of correlation coefficients into direct and indirect effects showed that characters viz ; days to maturity, boll weight, sympodia per plant, bolls per plant, plant height, uniformity ratio and upper half mean length had direct positive effect on seed cotton yield per plant. Thus, correlation and path analysis clearly indicated that direct selection based on number of bolls per plant, boll weight and number of sympodia per plant may be helpful in developing high yielding hybrids in arboreum cotton.

Keywords: Correlation, path coefficient analysis, cotton

Introduction

Cotton (*Gossypium spp.*) popularly known as “King of fibre” and “White Gold” is one of the most important commercial cash crops and plays a key role in economic, political and social affairs of the world. Cotton enjoys a pre-eminent status among all the cash crops in the country, being the principal material for flourishing textile industries. The predominant species cultivated in India is *G. hirsutum* which covers about 90% of the total area. India is maintaining the position of leading cotton growers in the world, China leading in terms of cotton production. Although cotton is cultivated in 77 countries; the five countries - China, India, United States, Brazil and Pakistan, produces 78% of the total world production from 72% of the world gross cotton area. China and Bangladesh are being the largest net importers of cotton (19% each) of the total world import, followed by Vietnam (17%), Indonesia (8%) and Pakistan (7%). United States maintaining leading exporter of cotton (36%) of the total world export, followed by Brazil (14%), India (10%) and Australia (9%). And the productivity front Australia leading with yield of 1814 kg/ha, followed by China (1726) and Brazil (1636) and India way behind at 507 kg lint/ha (AICCIP Annual Report, 2023-24). The ultimate objective of any breeder is to increase the yield and is normally a complex trait governed by polygenes. Hence, it is desirable for plant breeder to know the extent of relationship between yield and yield components which will facilitate in selecting desirable characteristics for yield improvement. Correlation coefficient analysis measures the magnitude of relationship between various plant characters and determines the component character on which selection can be based for improvement of seed cotton yield. Further, the true picture of correlation between seed cotton yield and other yield traits is reflected from direct and indirect effects in order to perceive the most influencing characters to be utilized as selection criteria in cotton breeding programme.

Material and Methods

The present study was carried out with 30 hybrids of cotton in randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications at Regional Agricultural Research Station, Lam, Guntur during *kharif*, 2023-24. The inter-row and intra-row spacing adapted was 60 cm x 30 cm. Each plot consisted of two rows of 6 m length. The row and plant spacing adapted were 60cm and 30cm, respectively. Recommended cultural practices were carried out and the crop was grown under uniform field condition to minimize environmental variations to the maximum possible extent. Observations were recorded on five randomly selected plants from each genotype per

replication for characters viz., days to flowering, days to maturity, plant height (cm), number of bolls per plant, number of sympodia plant per plant, boll weight (g) and seed cotton yield plant per plant (g). The fibre quality characters were analyzed at CIRCOT, Nagpur. The fiber quality traits were evaluated with HVI (High Instrument Volume). The analysis of variance was carried out following Panse and Sukhatme (1989)¹. Correlation coefficients between different characters were worked out as per Al-Jibouri *et al.* (1958). Genotypic correlation coefficients were further partitioned into direct and indirect effects by path analysis as suggested by Dewey and Lu (1959)¹.

Results and Discussions

The analysis of variance revealed highly significant differences among the hybrids for all the characters studied. The genotypic and phenotypic correlation coefficients and the genotypic and phenotypic path coefficients showing direct and indirect effects are presented in Table 1, 2 and 3 respectively. In general higher genotypic correlation coefficients than the phenotypic correlation coefficients were observed in the present study which is in conformity with the findings of Desalegn *et al.* (2009) who reported chief role of genetic effects. This indicated the strong inherent association between characters governed largely by genetic causes and is generally less subjected to environmental forces.

Computation of correlation between yield and yield attributing traits is of considerable importance in plant selection. The traits, number of bolls per plant, plant height, number of monopodia per plant, and boll weight were found to possess significant positive association with seed cotton yield per plant both at genotypic as well as phenotypic level. Therefore, selecting high yielding hybrids based on, number of bolls per plant, boll weight and number of sympodia per plant will be more useful. Similar results were reported by Hazem *et al.* (2005), Desalegn *et al.* (2009), Ahsan *et al.* (2014) and Gnanasekaran *et al.*, (2020), Jogender *et al.*, (2023).

In textile industry point of view, micronaire is very important because it shows fineness of the cotton fibre. In the present study, the traits days to 50% flowering, days to maturity and micronaire exhibited significant negative genotypic association with seed cotton yield. However, these results are in contradict with the earlier reports of Ramesh (2015), Vinodhana *et al.*(2013) who reported the ginning outturn had significant positive correlation with seed cotton yield. Whereas, seed index, micronaire value and bundle strength recorded non significant genotypic correlation with seed cotton yield per plant. However, correlation of yield and its components alone are not

adequate in any selection programme. The inter relationship among the individual character may ultimately influence the yield. In the present study, boll weight recorded significant positive association with number of sympodia per plant, number of bolls per plant, plant height, uniformity ratio, fibre strength, upper half mean length and ginning outturn at both phenotypic and genotypic levels indicating their true association. Similar results were also reported earlier by Alkuddsi *et al.* (2013), Rajamani *et al.* (2013) and Asha *et al.* (2015). Number of sympodia showed significant positive association with boll weight, number of bolls, plant height uniformity ratio, fibre strength, upper half mean length and ginning outturn at genotypic level. This was in accordance with the research findings of An *et al.* (2008), Kumar *et al.* (2010) and Sirisha *et al.* (2016). The traits, boll weight, number of sympodia per plant, number of bolls per plant, plant height, uniformity ratio, fibre strength, upper half mean length and ginning outturn also showed significant positive association with seed cotton yield per plant at both phenotypic and genotypic levels indicating the usefulness of these traits in selection programmes. Similar results were reported by Kishore *et al.* (2011) and Rajamani *et al.* (2013). Days to 50% flowering, days to maturity and micronaire value showed non-significant negative association with seed cotton yield per plant at both phenotypic and genotypic levels. This was in accordance with Pujer *et al.* (2014), Sirisha *et al.* (2016) and Gulhane and Wadikar (2017).

The correlation coefficient alone are insufficient to explain the relationship for effective manipulation of the characters, but path coefficient analysis furnishes a method for partitioning the correlation coefficient into direct and indirect effects and measures the relative importance of cause and effect relationship on seed cotton yield. The results of such analysis are discussed below.

In plant breeding, it is very difficult have knowledge of the effect of all component traits on expression of seed cotton yield. The residual effect permits precise explanation about the pattern of interaction of other possible components of yield. In other words, residual effect measures the role of the possible independent variables on the dependent variable which are usually not included in the study. In the present study, the residual effect observed at phenotypic (0.0.284) and genotypic (0.153) explains that the characters chosen for path analysis were adequate and appropriate. Among the characters studied, the traits *viz.*, plant height, number of bolls per plant, boll weight, sympodia per plant, uniformity ratio and upper half mean length showed direct positive effects besides expressing significant positive correlation with yield. Therefore, a direct selection of these traits would be useful. Therefore direct selection of these traits is suggested for obtaining seed cotton yield improvement. Similar kind of results were reported by Erande *et al.* (2014), Vinodhana *et al.* (2013), Preetha and Raveendran (2007), Ashok kumar and Ravikesavan (2010) and Dahiphale *et al.* (2018) showing positive and direct effect of one or other of above characters on seed cotton yield. However, significant negative direct effect was observed for days to flowering, fibre strength, micronaire and ginning out turn. Thus, these studies revealed that, the traits which had positive and direct effect on seed cotton yield should be given more emphasis for making selection for high yielding hybrids.

In the present study, number of bolls per plant exhibited positive indirect effect on seed cotton yield via number of sympodia, boll weight and plant height whereas boll weight exhibited positive indirect effect on yield via number of sympodia, boll per plant and plant height. Among the fibre quality traits, upper half mean length exhibited positive indirect effect on yield via uniformity ratio, ginning out turn and fibre strength via number of bolls per plant, boll weight, sympodia per plant and plant height. These results are in agreement with the findings of Kaushik *et al.* (2005), Iqbal *et al.* (2006), Gulhane and Wadikar (2017), Shruti *et al.*, (2020), Gauswami *et al.* (2021), and Sainath *et al.*, (2022).

Conclusion

The results discussed above indicate that correlation and direct and

indirect effect estimates vary for different traits with variation in genetic material based on seed cotton yield component traits and fibre properties. Hence, correlations, direct and indirect effect estimation would provide useful information for selecting traits of importance and planning successful breeding programme. If the genetic material is grouped for seed cotton yield and fibre quality characters, it is essential to devise suitable breeding techniques for simultaneous improvement of both seed cotton yield and quality parameters involving two way crosses, modified backcrosses or recurrent selection.

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Path diagram (Genotypic)

Path diagram (Phenotypic)

Table 1: Phenotypic (below diagonal) and genotypic (above diagonal) correlation coefficients for 12 characters among 30 hybrids of desi cotton (*Gossypium arboreum* L.) during *kharif*, 2023-24

Character	Days to flowering	Days to maturity	Boll weight (g)	Number of sympodia per plant	Number of bolls per plant	Plant height (cm)	Uniformity ratio	Fibre strength	UHML (mm)	Micronaire value (µg/inch)	Ginning outturn	Seed cotton Yield per plant (g)
Days to flowering	1.00	0.798**	-0.011	0.106	-0.120	-0.097	0.144	0.131	0.063	0.463**	-0.067	-0.031
Days to maturity	0.766**	1.00	-0.173	-0.037**	-0.342**	-0.249	-0.112	-0.038	-0.143	0.359**	-0.304*	-0.124
Boll weight (g)	-0.016	-0.184	1.00	0.535**	0.858**	0.730**	0.870**	0.864**	0.906**	-0.405**	0.710**	0.953**
Number of sympodia per plant	0.068	0.004	0.419**	1.00	0.603**	0.468**	0.562**	0.518**	0.491**	-0.054	0.510**	0.594**
Number of bolls per plant	-0.108	-0.319*	0.807**	0.515**	1.00	0.610**	0.766**	0.854**	0.838**	-0.404**	0.708**	0.861**
Plant height (cm)	-0.071	-0.244	0.689**	0.376**	0.547**	1.00	0.611**	0.706**	0.660**	-0.430**	0.586**	0.740**
Uniformity ratio	0.147	-0.115	0.839**	0.467**	0.734**	0.592**	1.00	0.791**	0.835**	-0.156	0.681**	0.797**
Fibre strength	0.132	-0.030	0.790**	0.424**	0.792**	0.663**	0.759**	1.00	0.915	-0.404**	0.628**	0.852**
UHML (mm)	0.058	-0.139	0.845**	0.383**	0.763**	0.609**	0.808**	0.866**	1.00	-0.278	0.716**	0.874**
Micronaire value (µg/inch)	0.434**	0.347**	-0.391**	-0.035	-0.394**	-0.412**	-0.161	-0.371**	-0.252	1.00	-0.464**	-0.454**
Ginning out turn(%)	-0.023	-0.246	0.529**	0.358**	0.560**	0.451**	0.558**	0.541**	0.555**	-0.347**	1.00	0.664**
Seed cotton yield per plant (g)	-0.029	-0.126	0.923**	0.489**	0.834**	0.703**	0.784	0.824**	0.842**	-0.44	0.556**	1.00

*Significant at 5% level and ** Significant at 1% level

Table2: Direct and indirect effects (phenotypic) of 12 characters on seed cotton yield among 30 genotypes of cotton (*Gossypium arboreum* L.) during *kharif*, 2023-24

Character	Days to flowering	Days to maturity	Boll weight (g)	Number of sympodia per plant	Number of bolls per plant	Plant height (cm)	Uniformity ratio	Fibre strength	UHML (mm)	Micronaire value (µg/inch)	Ginning outturn
Days to flowering	-0.1500	-0.1150	0.0025	-0.0102	0.0163	0.0107	-0.0221	-0.0199	-0.0087	-0.0652	0.0036
Days to maturity	0.1977	0.2580	-0.0477	0.0010	-0.0824	-0.0632	-0.0297	-0.0078	-0.0360	0.0895	-0.0636
Boll weight (g)	-0.0079	-0.0878	0.4751	0.1992	0.3838**	0.3274**	0.3987**	0.3756**	0.4015**	-0.1859	0.2513
Number of sympodia per plant	0.0032	0.0002	0.0195	0.0465	0.0240	0.0175	0.0218	0.0197	0.0178	-0.0016	0.0167
Number of bolls per plant	-0.0298	-0.0874	0.2209	0.1409	0.2735	0.1497	0.2009	0.2166	0.2088	-0.1079	0.1533
Plant height (cm)	-0.0103	-0.0354	0.0997	0.0544	0.0791	0.1446	0.0856	0.0960	0.0881	-0.0596	0.0654
Uniformity ratio	-0.0024	0.0019	-0.0135	-0.0075	-0.0119	-0.0096	-0.0161	-0.0123	-0.0130	0.0026	-0.0090
Fibre strength	-0.0085	0.0019	-0.0503	-0.0270	-0.0504	-0.0422	-0.0484	-0.0637	-0.0552	0.0236	-0.0345
UHML (mm)	0.0116	-0.0278	0.1688	0.0766	0.1524	0.1216	0.1614	0.1731	0.1997	-0.0503	0.1110
Micronaire value (µg/inch)	-0.0326	-0.0260	0.0294	0.0026	0.0296	0.0309	0.0121	0.0278	0.0189	-0.0750	0.0261
Ginning out turn(%)	-0.0009	-0.0089	0.0191	0.0129	0.0203	0.0163	0.0202	0.0196	0.0201	-0.0126	0.0361
Seed cotton yield per plant (g)	-0.0299	-0.1264	0.9234**	0.4894**	0.8343**	0.7038**	0.7843**	0.8247**	0.8420**	-0.4424**	0.5564**
Partial R ²	0.0045	-0.0326	0.4387	0.0228	0.2282	0.1018	-0.0127	-0.0525	0.1681	0.0332	0.0201

*Significant at 5% level, **Significant at 1% level, Residual effect = 0.284, Bold and diagonal values indicate direct effects

Table 3 : Direct and indirect effects (genotypic) of 12 characters on seed cotton yield among 30 genotypes of cotton (*Gossypium arboreum* L.) during *kharif*, 2023-24

Character	Days to flowering	Days to maturity	Boll weight (g)	Number of sympodia per plant	Number of bolls per plant	Plant height (cm)	Uniformity ratio	Fibre strength	UHML (mm)	Micronaire value (µg/inch)	Ginning outturn
Days to flowering	0.0159	-0.0127	0.0002	-0.0017	0.0019	0.0015	-0.0023	-0.0021	-0.0010	-0.0073	0.0011
Days to maturity	0.2456	0.3077	-0.0534	-0.0116	-0.1053	-0.0768	-0.0346	-0.0117	-0.0440	0.1105	-0.0937
Boll weight (g)	-0.0035	-0.0551	0.3177	0.1701	0.2728	0.2322	0.2766	0.2745	0.2879	-0.1287	0.2258
Number of sympodia per plant	0.0152	-0.0054	0.0765	0.1428	0.0862	0.0669	0.0804	0.0740	0.0702	-0.0078	0.0729
Number of bolls per plant	-0.0632	-0.1798	0.4514**	0.3174*	0.5256	0.3211*	0.4027	0.4489**	0.4408**	-0.2125	0.3722**
Plant height (cm)	-0.0240	-0.0616	0.1805	0.1156	0.1509	0.2470	0.1510	0.1744	0.1632	-0.1063	0.1447
Uniformity ratio	0.0161	-0.0125	0.0972	0.0628	0.0855	0.0682	0.1116	0.0884	0.0932	-0.0175	0.0761
Fibre strength	-0.1055	0.0307	-0.6960**	-0.4174**	-0.6879**	-0.5689**	-0.6377**	-0.8055	-0.7374	0.3254*	-0.5066**
UHML (mm)	0.0465	-0.1042	0.6599**	0.3580**	0.6108**	0.4811**	0.6083**	0.6667**	0.7283	-0.2030	0.5218**
Micronaire value (µg/inch)	-0.1634	-0.1267	0.1430	0.0192	0.1427	0.1519	0.0553	0.1426	0.0984	-0.3530	0.1638
Ginning out turn(%)	0.0211	0.0956	-0.2232	-0.1602	-0.2224	-0.1840	-0.2141	-0.1975	-0.2250	0.1458	-0.3140**
Seed cotton yield per plant (g)	-0.0311	-0.1240	0.9539**	0.5949**	0.8610**	0.7403**	0.7972**	0.8526**	0.8745**	-0.4545	0.6641**
Partial R ²	0.0005	-0.0381	0.3030	0.0850	0.4525	0.1829	0.0890	-0.6868	0.6369	0.1604	-0.2085

* Significant at 5% level, ** Significant at 1% level, Residual effect = 0.153, Bold and diagonal values indicate direct effects